

SIMULATED PRE-SERVICE TEACHER INTERNSHIP AS A MEANS OF CREATING CONDITIONS FOR PRESERVING MENTAL HEALTH AND WELL-BEING OF NOVICE TEACHERS IN PROFESSIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Budarina A.O., Degtyarenko K.A., Parakhina O.V.

The Immanuel Kant Baltic Federal University

In the context of modern challenges, the issue of developing, maintaining, and preserving the mental health and well-being of novice teachers in professional environment is considered to be extremely relevant.

The relevance of the problem of mental health and well-being of novice teachers is determined by the decisive role of the professional personality, the key characteristics of which include “a sufficient level of mental health and well-being of novice teachers: a positive attitude towards oneself and others, emotional-volitional stability and reflexivity” [5].

A teacher’s psychological health is more important than the professional competence, so this field should be staffed by “emotionally stable, reflective people with a good self-regulation and enthusiastic attitudes” [5].

Modern requirements for pre-service teacher training necessitate updating the forms and the content of the educational process as well as require the development of innovative technologies that enable adaptation to rapidly changing professional environments. For this purpose, various innovative methods and procedures have been implemented. Simulation is one of such kind of an advanced and innovative technique which is gaining its momentum worldwide these days in many contexts due to its numerous benefits [4]. It implies designing a dynamic and safe environment in which students can experiment within a variety of real world decision making situations related to the challenges of future career scenarios and successfully develop skills of applying theory to real world problems as well as use prerequisite skills for refining them in a nontraditional learning environment showing creativity in tackling natural quasi-professional problem-solving scenarios.

Simulation has been given a significant place in the curricula of teacher education at the Immanuel Kant Baltic Federal University. The research examines the best practices of implementing simulation training as a practical method of pre-service teacher training at the Institute of Education and Humanities, the largest structural subdivision of the Immanuel Kant Baltic Federal University, which performs the role of one of the key stakeholders in developing a regional educational system, setting educational policy of the region and providing teacher training in the region.

To create conditions for ensuring and maintaining mental health and well-being of novice teachers, as well as improving the quality of training for pre-teachers during their university studies and aligning students’ competencies with professional standards and modern labor market requirements, a module called “Simulated Pre-service Teacher Internship in Pedagogical Education” was introduced into educational programmes within “Pedagogical Education” and “Psychological and Pedagogical Education” training fields. This module is based on the implementation and promotion of new practical training formats in terms of simulating real-life teacher professional activities.

The case for pre-service teachers reveals options for integrating simulated internship into pre-service teacher educational programmes in such training fields as pre-school, primary, basic and secondary general education as well as speech therapy at the Institute of Education and Humanities [3].

A designed simulated pre-service teacher internship module considers a number of implementation models. These are:

Model 1. Simulated internship in a computer-generated technology environment.

Model 2. A person as a simulation (imitation model of an educational process agent).

Model 3. A set of parameters as a simulation.

Simulated pre-service teacher internship has significant educational and developmental potential in the context of modeling psychological and pedagogical conditions within the university environment, aimed at developing professional and personal competencies, including creating conditions for strengthening psychological health of novice teachers, which, according to modern research data, is one of the key tasks of the humanistic educational system, that introduces on-demand additional changes into the professional pre-service teacher training system when students are engaged into active learning activities which increases students’ motivation and engagement, develops skills in independent information search and professional problem solving. Under such conditions, students majoring in teaching begin to view their future profession as a calling connected to the development of the child’s personality, and a conscious sense of duty and a high degree of personal responsibility emerges.

Simulated pre-service teacher internship promotes developing the professional identity of pre-service teacher students during their training period at the university, initial professionalization of students through forming a positive attitude of students towards the chosen profession, and readiness to work effectively and successfully in the relevant professional field. Pre-service teachers’ professional identity is a critical factor in novice teachers’ motivation, effectiveness, and retention [2].

Simulated pre-service teacher internship has proved to possess a paramount importance in terms of developing students’ ability to pre-adapt [1], which implies the ability of a person throughout the life for self-development, self-education and self-reflexion in a rapidly changing world, displaying resilience to situations of uncertainty within future potential challenges. Of particular importance is a pre-service teachers’ ability to evaluate their own performance, identify problems, and find ways to overcome them, which helps identify strengths and areas for further improvement and supports a constant desire for self-improvement. Pre-adaptability skills presuppose the availability of resources and mechanisms that ensure successful adaptation to new conditions. This quality helps novice teachers successfully cope with professional tasks even in challenging circumstances, develop, maintain, and preserve mental health and well-being as well as achieve high results in their professional field.

References

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